

Classical and Quantum-Inspired Optimization for Strategic Public Expenditure Allocation

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Abstract

Strategic public expenditure allocation can be formulated as a combinatorial optimization problem under fiscal constraints and inter-project dependencies. This work investigates classical and quantum-inspired optimization methods for project portfolio selection. Project key performance indicators are translated into strategic, economic, and social impact scores, while synergy and redundancy relationships are explicitly modeled. Integer linear programming provides a deterministic optimal solution, whereas a quadratic unconstrained binary optimization model solved via simulated annealing process explores alternatively near-optimal portfolios. A simulated 50-project case study demonstrates that the two approaches offer complementary insights, enhancing robustness and strategic management in public expenditure allocation.

1. Introduction

Thailand's public budgeting process consists of four principal stages: planning and direction setting, budget proposal preparation, Cabinet and Parliament approval, and budget execution. Even though the Bureau of the Budget establishes the preliminary expenditure ceiling and issues guidelines requiring government agencies to formulate operational plans aligned with the National Strategy [1], the overall global index assessment and the national strategic goal of Thailand have progressed at a relatively modest pace [2]. With the insight analysis [3], this comes from the fact that the action plans and proposed projects attempt to link to the national strategy to demonstrate compliance with the requirements under the silo management style. In addition, key performance indicators (KPIs) focus mostly on the number of activities, and success is defined as the completion of projects and disbursement of budget according to targets. Given limited preparation time and resource constraints, an agentic artificial intelligence (AI) approach [4] can assist in transforming routine administrative KPIs into outcome-oriented metrics aligned with national strategic objectives and global benchmarks.

In the review and approval process, the proposed budgets are typically adjusted through multiple discussions and meetings to ensure that at least overall proposed budget stays within the budget limit. However, it would be highly desirable to simultaneously fine tune

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KPIs of proposed projects so that they strongly follow the criteria for basic plans, strategic plans, and joint or integrated plans [5], leading to strong collaboration amongst government agencies, and creating strategic, economic, and social impacts.

The overall process can be considered as a project selection and budget optimization process that mathematically finds the solutions to maximize or minimize an objective function under a set of constraints. Hence, this work explores classical and quantum-inspired optimization methods for project portfolio selection. The key idea is to translate the proposed KPIs into strategic, economic, and social values, and then model the selection of proposed projects as a combinatorial optimization problem. We show that classical integer linear programming (ILP) and quadratic unconstrained binary optimization (QUBO) can assist each other in project selection and budget optimization, ensuring robustness in strategic management.

2. Proposed Budget Optimization Framework

project_id	agency_name	project_name	budget_million	strategic_impact	economic_impact	social_impact
P01	MOPH	Project P01 (MOPH)	7830	9.6	7.7	6.8
P02	MFA	Project P02 (MFA)	5115	8.7	8	5.6
P03	MOL	Project P03 (MOL)	8337	9.2	9.5	6.2
P04	MC	Project P04 (MC)	6148	9.3	7.4	9.2
P05	MFA	Project P05 (MFA)	4958	9.1	8.8	8.9
P06	MOJ	Project P06 (MOJ)	6368	9.7	9.4	9.2
P07	MOED	Project P07 (MOED)	9616	7.6	8.4	5.2
P08	MOF	Project P08 (MOF)	7967	8.1	7.6	8.8
P09	MOD	Project P09 (MOD)	2215	9.5	8.1	7.3
P10	MDES	Project P10 (MDES)	872	7.1	7	5.4

(a)

project_a	project_b	relationship_score	type	description
P05	P33	-1.9	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P05 and P33
P35	P06	-2.5	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P35 and P06
P30	P22	-1.9	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P30 and P22
P36	P23	-1	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P36 and P23
P19	P48	-1.7	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P19 and P48
P14	P21	2.3	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P14 and P21
P09	P32	-2.1	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P09 and P32
P32	P24	2.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P32 and P24
P21	P50	-1.4	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P21 and P50
P01	P32	-0.8	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P01 and P32
P44	P23	1.6	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P44 and P23

(b)

Fig.1 Proposed data structures for project selection and budget optimization. a) Project metadata and (b) project relationship.

One important process in the framework is to translate typical proposed KPIs into strategic, economic, and social values. This can be obtained through focus group meetings and using AI. In addition, to make all government agencies into one team, the relationship score between projects is utilized. The aggregate project of the portfolio must also be under fixed budgetary constraint. Data structures are divided into two groups. The first group shows project details from each government agency. It contains project id, agency name, budget, strategic impact, economic impact, and social impact. The second data group highlights the relationship between projects or agencies. Type of project relationship consists of

redundancy with negative scores and synergy with positive scores. Description of the relationship is also shown but not used in the analysis.

2.1 Classical Integer Linear Programming

In this work, we propose to use classical ILP that is widely used in optimization applications [6]. It is a deterministic approach, treats the budget limit as the rigid wall, and provides the single mathematical best answer. In principle, it searches through all possible solutions and evaluates them until the best set of projects is found as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2 Principle of ILP for project selection and budget optimization.

2.1.1 Decision Variables

In the ILP model, binary variables are used for representation of discrete choices. Two types of variables are defined as follows.

A. Primary Variables: $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is used for project selection. $x_i = 1$ indicates that the project i is selected for funding and $x_i = 0$ means that the project i is rejected.

B. Auxiliary Variables: $z_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ represents interaction or relationship between projects. It helps handle “Synergy” and “Redundancy.” $z_{ij} = 1$ indicates that both projects i and j are selected, triggering the relationship score). $z_{ij} = 0$ means that the project i and j are less related to join force.

2.1.2 The Objective Function

The objective function is to maximize the total impact score and the relationship score. It can be mathematically expressed in the linear term as.

$$\text{Maximize } Z = \sum_i V_i \cdot x_i + \sum_{i \neq j} R_{ij} \cdot z_{ij}. \quad (1)$$

Here $V_i = (w_{stg} \cdot S_i) + (w_{econ} \cdot E_i) + (w_{soc} \cdot Soc_i)$ is a multi-dimensional impact score of project i . S_i, E_i , and Soc_i are the strategic, economic, and social impact scores of the project i , respectively. w_{stg}, w_{econ} , and w_{soc} are weighting values which their summation is equal to 1. R_{ij} is the relationship score (e.g., synergy or redundancy) between projects i and j . It allows the

model to see how agencies can work together, which is the cornerstone of a truly integrated plan or project.

2.1.3 Constraints

The first constraint is the budget. The sum of the budgets of all selected projects must not exceed the total available funds.

$$\sum_i C_i \cdot x_i \leq B_{limit}, \quad (2)$$

where C_i is the budget of project i . Another limiting variable is the coupling constraint z_{ij} between projects. It is equal to 1 only when both project i and j are selected.

2.1.4 Branch and Bound Solving Mechanism

In this work, an algorithm called Branch and Bound [7] is employed. It starts at the branching stage where it splits the problem into sub-problems (e.g., what if project P01 is selected? vs what if it isn't?). It then moves to the bounding and pruning process that calculates the best possible score for that branch. If the best possible score is worse than a solution already found, the solver prunes that entire branch. It continues until it mathematically proves that no better solution exists.

2.2 Quantum Simulation

It is realized that project selection and budget optimization can be considered as Knapsack problem [8]. This kind of combinatorial optimization problem is inherently suited for the potential of quantum computation [9-13]. In principle of quantum annealing process, the qubits start in a state where they represent all possible project combinations simultaneously. Each qubit represents its own project. The system tunnels through high-energy barriers searching for the deepest valley in the energy landscape. The system gradually settles into the global minimum, which corresponds to the most strategically optimized project selection and budget allocation as shown in Fig.3. It is a probabilistic approach where alternative appropriate solutions are found. In addition, the total budget of selected projects is negotiable meaning that it is not necessary to reach close to the budget limit.

Fig.3 Principle of quantum annealing for project selection and budget optimization.

In this approach, the decision variables and the objective function are like the ILP approach. Additional steps are required as follows.

2.2.1 Constraint Handling

Apart from the budget constraint in 2.1.3, QUBO converts the budget inequality into a penalty term “P”. This is to ensure that if the budget is exceeded, the energy of that state increases drastically, making the process of quantum computation avoid it.

$$P(x) = \lambda. (\sum_i C_i \cdot x_i + slack - B_{limit})^2. \quad (3)$$

Here λ is the penalty coefficient. It must be large enough to ensure that the budget condition is not broken, but not so large that it hides the strategic value. Slack is artificial variables used to compensate for the inequality. This implies that the total budget of the selected projects is not necessary to reach close to the budget limit.

2.2.2 The Final Hamiltonian

In quantum annealing process, the ground state (i.e., the lowest energy) is searching. As a result, the maximize problem is flipped into a minimization problem by multiplying -1 to Eqn(3). The Hamiltonian function can mathematically be expressed in terms of the objective function and the penalty term as.

$$H_{total} = - (\sum_i V_i \cdot x_i + \sum_{i<j} R_{ij} \cdot x_i x_j) + \lambda. (\sum_i C_i \cdot x_i + slack - B_{limit})^2. \quad (4)$$

The first term performs maximizing impact while the second term represents the budget constraint. This final form is also known as QUBO.

3. Experimental Proof of Concept

3.1 Data Preparation

The first data set is the project metadata that consists of the id of the project, the agency name, the project name, requested budget, strategic impact value, economic impact value, and social impact value. Fifty projects are simulated across 20 ministries in Thailand as shown in Table 1. In the simulation, w_{stg} , w_{econ} , and w_{soc} are assigned as 0.4, 0.4, and 0.2, respectively. B_{limit} is equal to 50,000 million Baht.

Another data set is simulated to show the relationship between projects (i.e., project_a and project_b) as shown in Table 2. This data set consists of project_a, project_b, relationship score, type of relationship, and description of the relationship. Only the relationship score is used during ILP and quantum analytical approaches. The experiment is performed using python programming on Google Colab.

Table 1 Project metadata

project_id	agency_name	project_name	budget_million	strategic_impact	economic_impact	social_impact
P01	MOPH	Project P01 (MOPH)	7830	9.6	7.7	6.8
P02	MFA	Project P02 (MFA)	5115	8.7	8	5.6
P03	MOL	Project P03 (MOL)	8337	9.2	9.5	6.2
P04	MC	Project P04 (MC)	6148	9.3	7.4	9.2
P05	MFA	Project P05 (MFA)	4958	9.1	8.8	8.9
P06	MOJ	Project P06 (MOJ)	6368	9.7	9.4	9.2
P07	MOED	Project P07 (MOED)	9616	7.6	8.4	5.2
P08	MOF	Project P08 (MOF)	7967	8.1	7.6	8.8
P09	MOD	Project P09 (MOD)	2215	9.5	8.1	7.3
P10	MDES	Project P10 (MDES)	872	7.1	7	5.4
P11	MOE	Project P11 (MOE)	9746	7.7	9.2	8.1
P12	MOJ	Project P12 (MOJ)	5116	8.6	8.5	7.7
P13	MOF	Project P13 (MOF)	5496	8.6	9.5	7.8
P14	MSDHS	Project P14 (MSDHS)	8822	7.4	8.2	5.4
P15	MOF	Project P15 (MOF)	5148	8.8	8.8	6.9
P16	MOC	Project P16 (MOC)	2725	7.6	6.5	9.2
P17	MOJ	Project P17 (MOJ)	2114	9.5	7.7	7.9
P18	MOE	Project P18 (MOE)	1656	8.7	8.4	5.3
P19	MC	Project P19 (MC)	9001	8.5	6.7	6.4
P20	MOED	Project P20 (MOED)	678	7.8	8.8	8.1
P21	MOE	Project P21 (MOE)	4690	8.5	7.6	6.6
P22	MOTS	Project P22 (MOTS)	2323	7.2	7	9.4
P23	MOF	Project P23 (MOF)	2098	9.1	9.1	9.3
P24	MC	Project P24 (MC)	7297	7.5	6.5	5.4
P25	MOTS	Project P25 (MOTS)	8606	9	8.3	8.9
P26	MNRE	Project P26 (MNRE)	6983	7.9	6.1	6.4
P27	MOT	Project P27 (MOT)	2982	9.7	8.9	7.9
P28	MOI	Project P28 (MOI)	2742	7.6	8.7	7.6
P29	MSDHS	Project P29 (MSDHS)	3090	8.4	7.2	9
P30	MI	Project P30 (MI)	1708	7.3	8.5	5.2
P31	MOAC	Project P31 (MOAC)	5359	8	7.5	5.2
P32	MFA	Project P32 (MFA)	1073	7.1	8.4	8.7
P33	MOT	Project P33 (MOT)	6119	9.1	7.8	9.4
P34	MOT	Project P34 (MOT)	2551	8.8	9.1	6.5
P35	MOC	Project P35 (MOC)	5189	7.2	7.8	7.5
P36	MOI	Project P36 (MOI)	7103	7.6	6.6	5.1
P37	MOC	Project P37 (MOC)	9567	7.3	7	7.9
P38	MNRE	Project P38 (MNRE)	7898	8.8	8.1	6.3
P39	MOED	Project P39 (MOED)	2901	7.4	6.6	6
P40	OPM	Project P40 (OPM)	1323	9.4	7.5	5.2
P41	MOPH	Project P41 (MOPH)	1284	9.7	7.3	8.8
P42	MOF	Project P42 (MOF)	601	7.8	9.3	5.9
P43	MOL	Project P43 (MOL)	7240	8.4	8.7	6.6
P44	MI	Project P44 (MI)	9753	8.5	7	5.6
P45	MOI	Project P45 (MOI)	5177	9.7	6.5	6.2
P46	MNRE	Project P46 (MNRE)	7319	8.5	7.2	7.3
P47	MOI	Project P47 (MOI)	4473	8.6	8.6	6.7
P48	MOTS	Project P48 (MOTS)	1325	9.1	8.9	8.2
P49	MDES	Project P49 (MDES)	2852	9.1	9.4	6.9
P50	MOPH	Project P50 (MOPH)	3807	7.6	7.6	7.3

Table 2 Project relationship

project_a	project_b	relationship_score	type	description
P05	P33	-1.9	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P05 and P33
P35	P06	-2.5	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P35 and P06
P30	P22	-1.9	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P30 and P22
P36	P23	-1	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P36 and P23
P19	P48	-1.7	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P19 and P48
P14	P21	2.3	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P14 and P21
P09	P32	-2.1	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P09 and P32
P32	P24	2.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P32 and P24
P21	P50	-1.4	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P21 and P50
P01	P32	-0.8	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P01 and P32
P44	P23	1.6	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P44 and P23
P08	P50	-2.4	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P08 and P50
P34	P36	-0.8	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P34 and P36
P49	P46	0.7	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P49 and P46
P44	P31	2.1	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P44 and P31
P40	P17	1.5	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P40 and P17
P11	P38	-0.4	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P11 and P38
P20	P44	1.1	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P20 and P44
P04	P19	2.6	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P04 and P19
P38	P15	-1.7	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P38 and P15
P06	P48	4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P06 and P48
P33	P48	0.9	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P33 and P48
P20	P22	1	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P20 and P22
P34	P07	-1.9	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P34 and P07
P09	P24	-0.7	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P09 and P24
P01	P11	-0.4	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P01 and P11
P39	P08	0.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P39 and P08
P29	P11	-1.9	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P29 and P11
P43	P12	-0.7	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P43 and P12
P50	P17	-2	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P50 and P17
P33	P14	-2.5	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P33 and P14
P47	P07	-1.8	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P47 and P07
P16	P38	2.8	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P16 and P38
P23	P47	0.5	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P23 and P47
P11	P16	-0.6	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P11 and P16
P27	P24	2.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P27 and P24
P20	P36	-1	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P20 and P36
P27	P49	3.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P27 and P49
P27	P15	3.7	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P27 and P15
P22	P26	1.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P22 and P26
P45	P41	0.6	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P45 and P41
P34	P13	2.3	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P34 and P13
P22	P12	2.8	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P22 and P12
P29	P50	-0.9	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P29 and P50
P26	P11	-0.8	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P26 and P11
P22	P08	3	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P22 and P08
P39	P17	3.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P39 and P17
P29	P43	1.7	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P29 and P43
P19	P36	3.3	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P19 and P36
P24	P13	3.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P24 and P13
P23	P01	-1.7	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P23 and P01
P01	P38	1.9	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P01 and P38
P19	P03	-1	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P19 and P03
P25	P12	-2.1	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P25 and P12
P16	P47	-0.8	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P16 and P47
P09	P22	0.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P09 and P22
P37	P22	3.8	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P37 and P22
P25	P26	-2.4	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P25 and P26
P44	P21	1.2	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P44 and P21
P31	P26	-2.9	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P31 and P26
P17	P31	-1.5	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P17 and P31
P12	P03	0.5	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P12 and P03
P13	P01	0.5	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P13 and P01
P19	P39	-0.8	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P19 and P39
P13	P22	-2.5	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P13 and P22
P34	P37	3.5	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P34 and P37
P45	P40	-2	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P45 and P40
P29	P04	0.6	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P29 and P04
P01	P09	1.7	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P01 and P09
P07	P23	3.1	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P07 and P23
P49	P47	-2	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P49 and P47
P05	P36	-1.5	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P05 and P36
P39	P20	0.5	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P39 and P20
P43	P32	3.6	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P43 and P32
P22	P32	-2.6	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P22 and P32
P21	P23	-1.6	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P21 and P23
P29	P45	2.4	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P29 and P45
P44	P04	3.1	Synergy	Strategic alignment between P44 and P04
P05	P50	-0.5	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P05 and P50
P45	P39	-2.9	Redundancy	Strategic alignment between P45 and P39

3.2 ILP Approach

In this scenario, an open-source library known as PuLP [14] is employed. It is widely used for optimization applications through linear programming and mixed-integer programming. As described in 2.1, the objective of maximization is established, and budget and logical coupling constraints are set. After that, the coin-or branch and cut solver is requested to execute the problem.

The strategic network graph (see Fig.4) displays nodes of selected projects. Projects with green line connected show synergic projects. Projects with redundancy relationship are connected with dash red lines. There are 22 selected projects with 11 project pairs and their relationship score of [P30-P22 (-1.9), P09-P32 (-2.1), P40-P17 (1.5), P20-P22 (1.0), P27-P49 (3.4), P27-P15 (3.7), P22-P12 (2.8), P39-P17 (3.4), P09-P22 (0.4), P39-P20 (0.5), P22-P32 (-2.6)]. A total budget of 49,377million Baht (98.75% of the budget limit) and 178.48 total impact score are determined. In this portfolio, the total relationship score is 10.1.

3.3 QUBO Approach

In this scenario, fifty qubits are simulated to represent projects 01-50. Additional qubits of 16 are used for slack variables. In addition, open-source Python softwares are employed including dwave-ocean-sdk which is designed to help formulate, solve, and analyze optimization problems using D-Wave's quantum annealing process [15], Qiskit Optimization that assists in automatically convert a combinatorial problem into QUBO format [16], and dwave-neal that functions as a simulated annealing sampler for approximate Boltzmann sampling or heuristic optimization [17].

During converting to QUBO format, the budget limit is converted into a penalty term. The penalty coefficient is automatically calculated by analyzing the maximum possible value the objective function can reach. It then sets the penalty coefficient to be slightly larger than that maximum value to ensure that violating a constraint always results in a higher energy state than any valid solution. To handle the "less than or equal to" condition of the budget, the converter adds approximately 16 slack qubits.

Fig. 4 Selected projects under ILP optimization.

Fig. 5 Selected projects under QUBO approach.

Unlike a deterministic approach, every time for operating this probabilistic approach, different project portfolios can be obtained. This is because the simulated (quantum) annealing explores an energy landscape to find the lowest point. In a complex problem involving 50 projects or more and multiple inter-project relationships, the energy landscape becomes jagged. The annealer might fall into a valley that is deep (i.e., a good solution) but not the deepest possible (e.g., the best solution). This results in a near-optimal selection of projects that differs from the ILP result. For example, the first run provides a set of 18 projects with a total budget of 45,225 million Baht (90.45%), a total relationship score of 12.1, and a 146.8 total impact score. In this section, only a project portfolio that gives a high total relationship score of 15.1 is shown in Fig.5. In this case, there are only 17 selected projects with a total budget of 49,023 million Baht (98.05%) and 138.36 total impact score. Only 10 projects can be pairs [P40-P17 (1.5), P06-P48 (4.0), P20-P22 (1.0), P50-P17 (-2.0), P27-P49 (3.4), P22-P26 (1.4), P22-P12 (2.8), P29-P50 (-0.9), P39-P17 (3.4), and P39-P20 (0.5)]. The remaining 7 projects are chosen to maximize the impact score without disturbing the budget limit and the total impact score.

It can be observed that ILP provides only one mathematically perfect answer based on the numbers provided. It tries to keep the total budget close to the budget limit. For quantum process, it often reveals alternative high-value portfolios. It can provide a set of projects that gives higher relationship score and less budget required than the ILP. If a project is chosen by ILP but consistently rejected by QUBO, it may be because that project is budget-efficient but sits in a very unstable part of the strategic relationship network. Having a set of diverse alternatives offered by quantum process might be more useful than one perfect answer. Results from hybrid classical and quantum approach can be assisted in the process of project selection, project revision, project synergic improvement, and budget optimization.

4. Conclusion

This work demonstrates the feasibility study of a hybrid classical-quantum optimization framework for government budgeting and project selection. By translating project KPIs into strategic, economic, and social impact scores and explicitly incorporating inter-project relationships, the budgeting process can be formulated as a structured combinatorial optimization problem. The classical ILP approach provides a deterministic, mathematically optimal solution under strict budget constraints, while the QUBO-based quantum-inspired approach reveals diverse near-optimal portfolios with alternative trade-offs between impact, collaboration, and budget utilization. The experimental results indicate that quantum optimization does not replace classical optimization but complements it by offering additional perspectives that are valuable in complex, multi-project or multi-agency decision environments. Such a hybrid approach can support more integrated planning, improve cross-agency collaboration, and enhance the strategic coherence of public expenditure. As quantum hardware and data availability continue to mature, this framework has strong potential to become a practical decision-support tool for adaptive and outcome-oriented public budgeting and project portfolio optimization.

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